

MULTIFACETED OF BAMBOO: ITS IMPACT ON HUMAN WELL-BEING, LIVELIHOOD AND THE ENVIRONMENT IN BARANGAY TANGKUAN, OMAR SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impact of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood, and the environment in barangay Tangkuan, Omar Sulu. Bamboo's sustainability benefits human health, promotes sustainable livelihoods, and creates a better environment. The main objective of this study is to investigate the ways in which bamboo can contribute to improving the quality of life and reducing poverty for small-scale farmers. The reviewed literature highlights the significant importance of bamboo in promoting human well-being, livelihood, and environmental sustainability. Bamboo offers versatile economic opportunities, contributes to climate change mitigation, and supports biodiversity conservation. A mixed qualitative and quantitative study involved 110 respondents, with 100 surveyed quantitatively and 10 interviewed qualitatively. The findings showed that bamboo positively impacts the well-being of the respondents as it promotes a better quality of life. It revealed that bamboo highly impacted the respondent's livelihoods as it served as a source of income. It also shows that bamboo also benefits the environment by serving as a natural water filter, improving water quality, and generating oxygen. The study recommends the government have training regarding bamboo in terms of livelihood, promoting bamboo-based livelihood opportunities within the community. Additionally, encouraging the residents to grow more bamboo in the barangay and providing training on proper planting, care, and maintenance. Furthermore, teaching and implementing for the class the significant effects of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood, and environment. Lastly, to encourage future researchers to further expand the study about the interconnectedness of human well-being, livelihood, and environment with regards to the impact of bamboo.

Keywords: *Bamboo, impact, well-being, livelihood, environment, MSU-Sulu*

INTRODUCTION

As far as grass goes, bamboo is the tallest grass on earth. As everyone knows, bamboo's sustainability has made it advantageous for human health. It is sustainable and can be used to construct homes and bamboo chairs, among other necessities for human habitation. According to (Kamiński, et. Al 2016) bamboo is a robust, quickly growing, and incredibly sustainable material. It is employed structurally in various regions of the world and can grow up to 25 meters in six months. A bamboo shoot or sprout (Dabung in Bahasa sug) is a portion of the plant that can be consumed. This exceptional growth rate allows for quick and efficient utilization of bamboo resources.

Bamboo has many possible applications, making it a vital resource for those in developing nations who are impoverished (Paudyal & Gurung, 2019). Its fibers are utilized in handicrafts, industry, and clothing manufacturing. Its shoots and sprouts are also used as food. It is a commonly used raw material. The most significant non-wood plant is bamboo, which grows widely over most of the tropical and subtropical regions. It has emerged as an especially important and superior replacement for produced wood composites, including veneer, plywood, particleboard, fiberboard, pulp and paper, and stripboards and matboards (Chaowana, 2013). Outside of forests, bamboo can be found extensively in agricultural regions, along riversides, alongside highways, and in urban settings. Since bamboo is a multipurpose, quickly growing, and renewable plant, it was thought to be a good substitute for forest-derived lumber. Its many uses as wood and wood products have substantially boosted the agricultural economy by giving the rural poor who cultivate it jobs and income, as well as by fostering community development and generating income for governments (Akwada, 2016).

Moreover, bamboo has several health benefits in addition to its positive effects on the environment. Bamboo, the Tausug term "Dabung," refers to the plant's edible shoots, which provide nutritive value and adaptability in the kitchen. These shoots are a nutritious food because they are high in fiber, vitamins, and minerals. In addition to a healthy diet, meals prepared with bamboo shoots can result in enhanced immunity, better digestion, and general health. The woody ringed stems, known as culms, are typically hollow between the rings (nodes) and grow in branching clusters from a thick rhizome (underground stem).

Additionally, bamboo is highly versatile. It is capable growing in a variety of soils derived from different parent rocks, within its climatic habitats. Bamboo has also been planted on a scale along roadsides and canals. It is also planted in degraded forest areas particularly near habitations.

The study aims to explore the context of Barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu, to understand the unique and diverse way in which bamboo influences human living and the surrounding ecosystem. Located in the province of Barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu, is known as for its Rich natural resources and cultural heritage. Bamboo a prominent natural resource in the area, hold immense potential for improving the lives of the locale community and contributing to the environmental sustainability. This study seeks to

provide valuable insights into the opportunities and challenges associated with bamboo utilization, in furthermore, this research will delve into the environmental conservation aspect of bamboo.

Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, field observation and community engagement, this study seeks to provide a clear understanding of the Multifaceted Impact of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood and the environment in Barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu

On the other hand, the local name of bamboo is called PATUNG in Bahasa sug term, KAWAYAN in Tagalog (Filipino) and the scientific name of bamboo, BAMBUSOIDEAE. It is a subfamily of flowering perennial plants in the grass family POACEAE. There are various genera and species of bamboo. Each with its own scientific name, some common genera of bamboo include PHYLLOSTACHYS, DENDROCALAMUS, and BAMBUSA. The finding of the research will contribute to the knowledge base on bamboo utilization, inform local stakeholders and policymakers, and guide sustainable development initiative that harness the potential of bamboo for the benefits of the community and the preservation of the environment.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the ways in which bamboo can contribute to improving the quality of life and reducing poverty for small-scale farmers. It also examines the role of bamboo in preserving ecosystems, conserving soil, and providing benefits. Additionally, the study explores how bamboo cooperatives can positively impact soil conservation efforts. Furthermore, it explores the potential for rehabilitating lands

On review literature of the researchers, it becomes evidence that there is a lack of local study focusing on the multifaceted impacts of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood and environment. The interaction of these factors provides researchers with insights into potential trade-offs or synergies, as well as strategies to improve well-being, encourage sustainable livelihoods, and reduce negative environmental impacts.

To achieve sustainable environmental interventions, it is crucial to understand how well-being, livelihoods, and environments interact with each other.

Research Questions:

The primary goal of this study is to determine the multifaceted impact of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood, and environment in Barangay Tangkuan, Omar Sulu. The following are the questions to achieve the goal of the study:

1. What is the impact of bamboo on well-being?
2. What is the impact of bamboo on the Livelihood?
3. What is the impact of bamboo on the environment?
4. In what ways does bamboo become multifaceted on the human live

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a mixed methods approach, combining qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys to gain a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted impact of bamboo on the specified aspects in the mentioned Barangay. The qualitative interviews provided in-depth insights, while the quantitative surveys offered statistical data to support the findings. This process aimed to capture a holistic understanding of the impact of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood, and the environment of Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu.

Mixed methods research is a sort of study where researchers integrate components of qualitative and quantitative research procedures for the general goals of understanding and corroboration (Johnson et. al., 2007). It involved using questionnaires to gather specific types of information about a particular subject. Furthermore, this method helped the researchers investigate the Multifaceted of bamboo: its impact on human well-being, livelihood and the environment in Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu.

Research site

This study was conducted at Omar, Luuk Sulu North East, Philippine, a seaside area in the province of Sulu. The researchers chose the place of implementation due to its convenience when it comes to gathering the data. This study was connected at barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu which under the care of Barangay chairman, Radjabon S. Abun.

The barangay Tangkuan is located at Omar, Sulu. Its population as determined by the census 2020 was 2,608. This presented 9.29% of the total population of Omar, Sulu. Elevation at these coordinates is estimated at 25.5 meters or 83.7 feet above mean sea level. From Jolo to Omar are 56 km by road.

Participants

The participants for this study were the residents of Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu, Philippines. The selection process involved engaging with community leaders and members to ensure a diverse representation of individuals involved in various aspects of bamboo-related activities, including bamboo farming, crafts, and conservation efforts. By targeting individuals with knowledge and experience in these areas, the researchers used purposive sampling to ensure that the participants could provide valuable insights and data relevant to the study objectives. With a total of 2,608 residents in the said Barangay as determined by the census 2020, 10 residents were selected for interviews (Qualitative), while 100 residents were surveyed (Quantitative). The reason for the selection of these participants is because they are the bamboo experts in the barangay and have experience in bamboo cultivation and utilization.

Instrumentation

A survey questionnaire was used as a research tool. In survey research, questions are usually closed-ended or include rating scales to collect uniform data. The survey questions were designed by the researchers based on the various information collected and consisted of a series of questions for respondents. Quantitative survey data was obtained using a 4-point Likert scale as follows: 4-Strongly Agree (SA); 3-Agree (A); 2-

Disagree (D); 1-Strongly disagree (SD). The survey questionnaires are divided into three parts. 1. Multifaceted of Bamboo: Its Impact on Human Well-being, 2. Multifaceted of Bamboo: Its Impact on Livelihood, 3. Multifaceted of Bamboo: Its Impact on the Environment in Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu. The fourth part is the last part of the research and is conducting interviews. Guiding questions for the interview portion included exploring personal experiences and perspectives on the diverse impacts of bamboo on human well-being, livelihood, and the environment in the community of Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu.

Data Collections

Due to the off-campus nature of the study, the researchers wrote a letter to the school director, Dr. Norman A. Abdurahman, to request permission. The researchers have also prepared a letter for the Barangay chairman of the Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu, Radjabon S. Abun to seek their approval for conducting the research in their area, Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu. This is to ensure that the research is legal, correct, and follows the proper process without violating any regulations in gathering the information needed. Each member of the group has sought permission from their respective parents to avoid any misunderstandings. Aside from going through the legal process, the researchers thoroughly planned their research as it is located far from the school. They made sure that their safety is prioritized and far from any potential hazards.

Statistical techniques

To study the impact of bamboo in Omar Sulu, descriptive statistics helped the researchers summarize the collected data. The tool that was employed was only the weighted arithmetic mean to assess the over research questions "What is the impact of bamboo on human well-being", "What is the impact of bamboo on livelihood", "What is the impact of bamboo on environment"

The researchers used thematic analysis to assess the research question "In what ways does bamboo become multifaceted on human lives". By using this statistical tool, the researchers aimed to gain valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of bamboo, its impact on human well-being, livelihood, and the environment in Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 Impact of Bamboo on Human Well-being

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I believe that using bamboo products makes my life better.	3.6	0.5	Strongly Agree
2. I believe that incorporating bamboo-based materials in my home décor contributes to a healthier living.	3.3	0.5	Strongly Agree
3. I believe that supporting the use of bamboo positively impacts my overall well-being by contributing to a more sustainable and eco-friendly world.	3.2	0.5	Agree
4. I believe that supporting the bamboo industry contributes to the well-being of local communities and economies, which in turn affects my own well-being.	3.2	0.5	Agree
5. I believe that practicing sustainable living through the use of bamboo products positively impacts my overall well-being.	3.2	0.5	Agree
6. I believe that using bamboo as a natural, organic material positively impacts my	3.1	0.4	Agree
7. I believe that using bamboo products such as bamboo clothing and bedding, positively impacts my physical and mental well-being.	3.1	0.7	Agree
8. I believe that using bamboo kitchenware and utensils will reduce exposure to harmful chemicals.	3.0	0.7	Agree
9. I believe that bamboo-based skincare and beauty products help maintain my skin healthier.	2.5	1	Disagree
10. I believe that utilizing bamboo-based healthcare products, such as bamboo charcoal, is good for the health.	2.5	1	Disagree
Total	3.1	0.6	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75=SD; 1.76-2.50=D; 2.51-3.25=A; 3.26-4.00=SA

The overall weighted mean of the impact of bamboo on human well-being in barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu is 3.1 and interpreted as "agree". This means that the residents in the said barangay "agree" that the presence of bamboo has highly impacted

their well-being, and this also means that the majority of the respondents were likely to match their experience with how bamboo helps their well-being. Among the questionnaire items, the statement "I believe that using bamboo products makes my life better" ranks highest with an average weighted mean of 3.6 and interpreted as strongly agree, while the statement "I believe that utilizing bamboo-based healthcare products, such as bamboo charcoal is good for the health" ranks lowest with an average weighted mean of 2.5 and interpreted as disagree.

Bamboo has been shown to have a good impact on wellbeing. Research shows that using wind to swing kinetic facades made of bamboo can provide background noise that supports the user's well-being and minimizes glare from sunlight, boosting the overall atmosphere and quality of rest in an apartment. (Ongkojoyo et. al., 2023). The findings of our study were likely reveals that bamboo plays a significant role in the practices of the local community, contributing to their overall well-being and sense of identity.

Table 4.2 Impact of Bamboo on Livelihood

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. Bamboo cultivation provides me with a sustainable source of income.	3.5	0.6	Strongly Agree
2. Bamboo weaving and handicrafts preserve traditional skills and cultural heritage for me.	3.5	0.6	Strongly Agree
3. Bamboo products have a beautiful and natural look, perfect for home design.	3.5	0.5	Strongly Agree
4. The production of bamboo crafts and bamboo products generates additional income for me	3.5	0.5	Strongly Agree
5. Bamboo plantations provide me with a renewable source of construction materials.	3.4	0.5	Strongly Agree
6. I believe bamboo cultivation helps the local economy	3.4	0.5	Strongly Agree
7. Bamboo weaving and handicrafts preserve traditional skills and cultural heritage for me.	3.4	0.5	Strongly Agree
8. Bamboo products are durable and eco-friendly, making them a great choice for sustainable living.	3.3	0.5	Strongly Agree
9. Bamboo harvesting and processing generate jobs, while bamboo-based products present a wide range of business opportunities	3.3	0.5	Strongly Agree

10. Bamboo-based livelihoods contribute to poverty alleviation in my community.	3.2	0.5	Agree
Total	3.4	0.5	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75=SD; 1.76-2.50=D; 2.51-3.25=A; 3.26-4.00=SA

Overall, the impact of bamboo on livelihood as perceived by the residents of barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu gained a "strongly agree" with an overall weighted mean of 3.4 and was interpreted as "strongly agree." Among each situational/action statement or item given, the item "bamboo cultivation provides me a sustainable source of income" ranked first with an average weighted mean of 3.5, but the item "bamboo-based livelihood contributes to poverty alleviation in my community" ranked the lowest with an average weighted mean of 3.2 in the study on the impact of bamboo on livelihood in barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu, and 3.4 is the overall average weighted mean.

Bamboo has a tremendous impact on livelihoods, delivering numerous socioeconomic benefits to communities. It is used for construction, handicrafts, fencing, musical instruments, and ceremonies, among other things, contributing to the income and livelihoods of people in many places. The findings of (Ayer et. al., 2023), underscore the importance of sustainable management and utilization of bamboo resources to ensure the long-term viability of livelihood opportunities and the preservation of cultural practices linked to bamboo. Based on the results and the literature, it has been proven that bamboo makes a significant contribution to society and the lives of individuals.

Table 4.3 Impact of Bamboo on the Environment

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I saw that bamboo acts as a natural water filter, improving water quality.	3.6	0.6	Strongly Agree
2. I believe that growing bamboo helps reduce deforestation	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
3. I believe that bamboo products are good for the environment as they are biodegradable and help reduce waste. Examples of these products include beddings, kitchen utensils, and furnitures made out of bamboo.	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
4. I understand that bamboo forests provide habitats for various plants and animal species and support the balance of ecosystems.	3.4	0.5	Strongly Agree

5. I appreciate bamboo as a renewable resource that grows quickly, making it an environmentally friendly choice.	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
6. I understand how growing bamboo promotes soil conservation and prevents erosion.	3.3	0.5	Strongly Agree
7. I believe that growing bamboo can help save other trees.	3.3	0.4	Strongly Agree
8. I believe that growing bamboo helps reduces the carbon in the air.	3.3	0.5	Strongly Agree
9. I recognized the use of bamboo as a sustainable alternative to wood that reduces deforestation.	3.2	0.6	Agree
10. I am aware that growing bamboo requires minimal use of pesticides and fertilizers, which reduces chemical pollution.	3.1	0.5	Agree
Total	3.3	0.5	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75=SD; 1.76-2.50=D; 2.51-3.25=A; 3.26-4.00=SA

Table 3 presents the result of the computation of the impact of bamboo on the environment. The statement "I saw that bamboo acts as a natural water filter, improving water quality" has the highest average weighted mean of 3.6 among the ten items and is interpreted as "strongly agree" and the item "I am aware that growing bamboo requires minimal use of pesticides and fertilizers, which reduces chemical pollution" got the lowest rank with an average weighted mean of 3.1 and is interpreted as "Agree". The overall average weighted mean is 3.3 and interpreted as "Strongly Agree". This means that the environment in barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu has highly impacted by the presence of bamboo as it served as their natural water filter, improves their water quality, and it produced large amount of oxygen.

The use of bamboo in construction can help reduce carbon emissions and promote sustainable building practices. Overall, bamboo has the potential to be a sustainable and environmentally benign resource used in a variety of applications, including construction and pollution control (Shiwani and Thanganami, 2023). It was similar to the article constructed that the utilization of bamboo in construction offers a sustainable alternative to traditional building materials. Incorporating bamboo in construction can help reduce carbon.

4.4 In your own opinion, how did you define bamboo as a useful material base on your experience?

T1 Bamboo utilization for constructing houses

R1: I will tell you about the importance of bamboo here in the countryside. The bamboo here is necessary for us to construct a house. (Excerpt 1).

R2: It can also be used to construct a house. (Excerpt 2).

R3: Bamboo holds great significance for us humans because it can be utilized to build a house. (Excerpt 3).

R5: Most people here use bamboo to make a house. (Excerpt 4).

R5: As I said we use it to make a house. That's the only importance of bamboo, it can help people and can be used for livelihood. (Excerpt 5).

R6: Bamboo here in our province is used to make houses. (Excerpt 6).

R7: For me, based on what I have experienced, the use of bamboo is used to make lodgings such as floors (lantay in Bahasa sug term) and bamboo blinds (tiyadtad in Bahasa sug term). (Excerpt 7).

R8: The important thing that bamboo gives to our livelihood is like the house we can make from bamboo. (Excerpt 8).

R10: When it's big, it can be made into a complete house, it can be made into floors, walls and can be made into a roof. That's all I can say about bamboo. (Excerpt 9).

R10: As they say, you can make a house that is all made of bamboo, you just have to make a knot, then make a hole in the bamboo and fasten it. (Excerpt 10).

The participants emphasized the utilization of bamboo as a sustainable constructing material for constructing houses and contributing to a sustainable living. According to (Madhushan et. al., 2023), bamboo is a multipurpose material that can be utilized to make fences, floors, walls and chairs.

T2 Bamboo utilization for making handicrafts

R1: It can be used for making floors, for making fences, for making walls, and we also used it to make bamboo chairs beside our house. (Excerpt 11).

R2: It can be utilized to make bamboo fish traps (bubuhan in bahasa sug term), which are used to catch fish and lobster, and it can also be used to make a fence like what the old folks do. (Excerpt 12).

R2: It can be utilized to make bamboo baskets (ambung in bahasa sug term), bamboo nets (ligu in bahasa sug term), bamboo closets (paradul in bahasa sug term), and also bamboo chairs. (Excerpt 13).

R3: It can create fish nets (called bungsud in Bahasa Sug), as well as crab traps (called tutung in Bahasa Sug). This implies that it will facilitate our way of life. (Excerpt 14).

R4: Bamboo can be utilized into various ways like for making floors, making bamboo baskets (ambung in bahasa sug term), bamboo fish dryer (siklat in bahasa sug term) and bamboo shelf (paga-paga in bahasa sug term). (Excerpt 15).

R4: You can make fish traps (bubuh in Bahasa sug term), make crab traps (tugung in Bahasa sug term) if in the sea. (Excerpt 16).

R5: Bamboo can be made in different ways such as flat bamboo baskets (ligu in bahasa sug term) the flat bamboo basket is necessary to separate the rice and its skin called winnowing, and then it can be made into a strainer. Many things can be done with bamboo, we are making this bamboo xylophone. That's all I can say that I experienced working with bamboo. (Excerpt 17).

R5: Firstly here in barangay Tangkuan, it will be good for us, bamboo is a big help because it provides livelihood as well if there are projects, the teachers are in need and then the young people bring them to make projects made of bamboo such as glasses, that is the importance of bamboo. (Excerpt 18).

R6: Bamboo here in our province is used to make a crab traps (panggal in Bahasa Sug terms), and fish traps (tugung in Bahasa Sug terms). The "panggal" is used to catch crabs, and the "tugung" is used to catch fish. The bamboo is also used to make a hook for catching shrimp and to make a bow. Here we have bamboo, which is used for fencing and also for carrying dead people (Janaja in Bahasa Sug term). (Excerpt 19).

R6: Bamboo is helpful in our barangay because it can be used to make things and utensils like glasses, ladles, mugs, and so on. And it also gives us a living. (Excerpt 20).

R7: Apart from using it to construct a house, it is made into bamboo nets (ligu in bahasa sug term) it is a traditional strainer. Additionally, bamboo can serve as an alternative rice cooker which is called (lut in bahasa sug term), it can also be made into bamboo poles to get coconuts, cover for machete (taguban in bahasa sug term), fish nets (bungsud in bahasa sug term) to catch fish and crabs. Furthermore, it can also be used as a stick to penetrate roasted bananas. It can give convenience to people, just like chairs. (Excerpt 21).

R8: I make this as a fence and bamboo roof, that's all I can do made of bamboo. (Excerpt 22).

R8: We make it a wall and a grille, because this is where bamboo can provide comfort. (Excerpt 23).

R8: What bamboo can do is fish traps (bubuh in bahasa sug term), crab traps (panggal in bahasa sug term) and bed. (Excerpt 24).

R8: The importance of bamboo is that I make it into chicken coop and shelf. (Excerpt 25).

R9: The first thing here is to cut the bamboo into pieces, then bend the bamboo to make a fish trap (tugung in tausug term). The purpose of this is to catch some crabs and palu palu fish; you just have to submerge the trap in the river. (Excerpt 26).

R9: Fish trap (tugung in bahasa sug term) is hard to make because I am the one who knows how to make it here in our province. The process of making the fish trap is that you have to bend it first, then cut it into thin sticks, then weave the thin sticks to make the fish trap (tugung in bahasa sug term). (Excerpt 27).

R9: The people here will harvest it because they need it to make bamboo fish traps (tugung in bahasa sug term). (Excerpt 28).

R9: The only importance of bamboo is utilized to make fish traps (tugung in Bahasa Sug terms). (Excerpt 29).

Additionally, it appears that even bamboo can be used to utilize fish, crabs and lobster traps making it beneficial for the individuals in the said barangay as they can be used it as an alternative fish net. In addition, it reveals that bamboo can be used to make various types of handicrafts that are necessary to them and can make their lives less difficult. Bamboo is becoming more widely recognized as a sustainable and adaptable resource for human usage. It is a renewable material that may be used in numerous lifestyle goods like construction, furniture, handicrafts and even foods (Prasad and Muthusamy, 2023). Bamboo can be utilized to make fish traps, offering a less expensive option than conventional materials and possibly bringing in money for rural communities (Li and Haolle, 2015).

4.5 In bamboo cultivation, in what way did you make bamboo as a source of income?

T1 Utilizing bamboo coracles to plant sea moss

R2: The bamboo here in the countryside means that after we harvest it, we will cut it, bring it to the seaside, and use it to make coracles (alul in bahasa sug term) to plant our sea moss. (Excerpt 30).

R4: It can be made into coracles, it can be used when planting sea moss, it can be a source of income. (Excerpt 31).

R5: Then what we do is we bring it to the seaside to sell it to those who plant sea moss for them to use in planting. (Excerpt 32).

R7: For making coracles (alul in bahasa sug term) to plant sea moss to sell. (Excerpt 33).

R8: There are also other bamboos brought to the beach to be used in planting sea moss. (Excerpt 34).

The participants highlight the use of bamboo; they bring it to the coast to make coracles that are used to plant sea moss. A bamboo-based planting apparatus can be used to cultivate sea moss. This unique system incorporates perforations in bamboo joints where a culture unit is put, allowing plants to grow without soil and preventing

contamination from soil heavy metals (Qin et. al., 2019). Furthermore, a fully automated floating refuse removal boat equipped with a hydraulic large item grabbing machine can help maintain sea moss cultivation areas by efficiently removing debris and trash from the water (Huang et. al., 2015). Furthermore, a bamboo fungus planting method can increase sea moss yield by using a particular fungous material mixture and implanting it in appropriate habitats, hence boosting sea moss quality while conserving land (Yan et. al, 2015).

T2 Bamboo as a source of income

R2: As a source of income, I only used bamboo to catch crabs. (Excerpt 35).

R3: The bamboo will be turned into a bamboo roof; all that has to be done by stitching it, and customers will purchase it from us. Second, since our area has bamboo plantations, the people who live by the sea will need bamboo to catch fish, which they will then purchase. (Excerpt 36).

R3: If you are good at making decorations, you can also make it a source of income, making beds and chairs, you can make it a source of income. (Excerpt 37).

R3: Our experience in our province indicates that bamboo is important because in order to obtain coconuts, people will first pick small bamboo and use them to create a pole with a small machete on top and make it as a source of revenue. (Excerpt 38).

R4: If bamboo is sold, it can help with living such as bamboo shoots (dabung in bahasa sug term) can also be sliced and made into vegetables to eat. (Excerpt 39).

R6: This bamboo helps to provide another livelihood, like selling a lot. The plant can be made into vegetables and eaten, and bamboo is worth fifty, so bamboo can provide a livelihood. (Excerpt 40).

R6: The plants are cut to eat, and then you can sell them in the market because they can provide a source of income. (Excerpt 41).

R6: If the use of bamboo can make a chair to be used for sitting and resting, then there is a chance that it can be sold like what is sold in the town. (Excerpt 42).

R7: For me, bamboo can be a source of income, dig the soil just like how bamboo is planted, and then after that we have something to make a living. Why? When you harvest it, you can make a fence for crops such as sweet potatoes and pineapples, you will have to earn money and i can spend it on myself and my children. (Excerpt 43).

R7: Like a fish trap (panggal in Bahasa sug term) it is one of our incomes, meaning this fish trap is a big help for me because it is my livelihood. (Excerpt 44).

R8: As we are used to, lobster traps (tugung in bahasa sug term), fish traps (panggal in bahasa sug term) and what so called "bugyas in bahasa sug term" become the source of income. (Excerpt 45).

R9: The purpose of bamboo for our livelihood is to make fish traps (tugung in bahasa sug term) to catch some fish called palu-palu and crabs. Fish trap making and catching fish can be a source of income by selling the fish for 50 pesos. By doing that, the fisherman will have money by selling what they catch. (Excerpt 46).

R10: Bamboo is expensive because everyone needs it and many need it. (Excerpt 47).

Based on the participant's narratives, bamboo is a very useful material for human needs. It can generate revenue in a number of ways. Bamboo is particularly advantageous since it enables the locals to earn money for a variety of uses, such as a profitable source of revenue. This money may be used to pay for their daily essentials. For rural communities, bamboo has the potential to generate income that would allow them to purchase necessities (Ekwe et. al., 2022). Bamboo is essential for socioeconomic benefits in places like Ethiopia, where it is used as building material.

4.6 Can you share any personal experiences or stories about how bamboo cultivation or utilization has improved livelihood opportunities in your barangay?

T1 Bamboo as fences to protect the crops

R1: Our experience in cultivating bamboo is that we will take small ones, like the size of our arm, and after that, we will plant them and put up a fence so that the cows don't eat them and the bamboo will grow freely. (Excerpt 48).

R1: In our experience, we can use bamboo to make fences, and we will use it to fence our crops such as bananas and sweet potatoes (Excerpt 49).

R3: As for bamboo, from what we've seen so far, it's getting a little scarcer because the cattle have already eaten some of it. This makes it harder for us to make a living because we want to be able to sell something, but the animals eat the bamboo. (Excerpt 50).

R3: Initially, we can prioritize things like fencing our vegetable and banana plantations if we haven't been provided an iron fence. That is why we value bamboo so much (Excerpt 51).

R5: Bamboo should be appreciated as well as those to be planted, because as we say here in the countryside, the planting of bamboo is a big help in our lives because, without bamboo, our life here is difficult. (Excerpt 52).

R6: To plant bamboo, you also need to build a yard so that cows and goats don't eat the plants. (Excerpt 53).

R7: Here with us, the bamboo must be fenced because it is eaten by wild cattle, so it must have a fence to protect the bamboo and grow properly. The bamboo is fenced with the bamboo itself so that it cannot be eaten by the animals. (Excerpt 54).

The participants claim that bamboo in their area is becoming scarcer since cows have already eaten it. They also advised that when growing bamboo, you should fence it to prevent cattle from eating it. Livestock grazing can have a substantial impact on

bamboo production. Furthermore, cultivation practices can influence carbon storage in bamboo ecosystems, with grazing causing soil carbon reduction and necessitating the use of sustainable management practices to maintain harmony between environmental improvement and soil productivity (Caf and Beijing, 1994).

4.7 As a user of bamboo, aside from building houses what materials can you produce from bamboo?

T1 Bamboo durability

R7: Besides building a house, there are many things you can make furniture or materials out of bamboo, first here among people like you who live in the city. The things you use are hollow blocks and they need money to buy, but I am guaranteed bamboo rather than iron. If the iron will last for 30 years, then bamboo will last 50 years. (Excerpt 55).

R10: Bamboo can be mixed with cement if the sand is new, bamboo is stronger because we tried it. That is the only importance of bamboo. (Excerpt 56).

The participants reported that bamboo's durability can last longer than iron. They also emphasized that bamboo is able to be mixed with cement if the sand is new. According to the research findings, bamboo can survive longer than iron in some applications. Bamboo has been found to have lower life cycle costs than corrugated galvanized iron sheets, making it a more environmentally friendly roofing material (Hailu et. al., 2022).

T2 Bamboo as an alternative fire lighter

R7: Bamboo can be utilized in many things like for making fire because it can serve as an alternative lighter according to the old folks. The step in doing it is you just have to get the part of the coconut which is the mesocarp (bunut in bahasa sug term) and after that, put the dry mesocarp into the bamboo and start to massage it hard with force for a minute then if it starts to smoke, it means the fire is ready. (Excerpt 57).

R7: Bamboo can light a fire by putting it into the skin of bamboo. Here with us even without everything, if there is no match, we can light up the fire by using the bamboo and mesocarp (bunut in Bahasa sug term). (Excerpt 58).

The participants assert that bamboo can be utilized to light up fire by just using its node and coconut mesocarp. Bamboo generates heat when burned through its mesocarp due to a sequence of occurrences caused by various heat fluxes. Heating bamboo perpendicular or parallel to the grain produces a variety of effects, including moisture movement, pyrolysis, oxidation, and flame (Ian et. al., 2021).

4.8 For you how has the use of bamboo as a construction material provided sustainable and eco-friendly housing solutions in Barangay Tangkuan Omar, Sulu?

T1 Bamboo as a sustainable building material and environmentally beneficial housing option

R1: After we harvest the bamboo, we will cut it, and then measure the size of the house that we will be constructing. After that, we will split it to make bamboo floors from the porch down to the kitchen. (Excerpt 59).

R2: The purpose of constructing bamboo materials is for convenience, like utilizing chairs for resting, which are made out of bamboo; making walls; and making floors, which are where I sleep. (Excerpt 60).

R3: First, if they don't have a metal roof, it will simply be sewed into a bamboo roof (atup sani in Bahasa Sug). Next, it will be fashioned into a wall and, finally, a floor. That's all building a house entails. (Excerpt 61).

R4: Firstly, the bamboo must be matured before it can be used, if it is not yet ripe, it cannot be used, it will withered. The bamboo, if it is very old you will know it too, you just have to slam it or by just looking at it you will know it. If it makes a sound, it means the bamboo is very old. (Excerpt 62).

R5: Making a house, when you harvest bamboo you cut it and then you measure how many lengths you need to make the walls and then make the floors of the house to be used here in the barangay tangkuan. (Excerpt 63).

R6: Planting bamboo and using it gives us good things because, first of all, we build a house; it provides fresh air and coolness near our house; and we can provide livelihoods made of bamboo. (Excerpt 64).

The participants emphasize the utilities of bamboo in building materials after you harvest it they assert that the purpose of bamboo is for their convenience which they likely used and their eco-friendly constructions material. Traditional bamboo construction techniques have been widely used in rural areas for decades and are frequently associated with vernacular architecture (Xiuyuan and Zhang, 2023). Bamboo is gaining popularity as a sustainable building material due to its biodegradability, Bamboo is undoubtedly a substantial source of income for many people. Bamboo plays an important role in rural areas such as Bhadrak district, Odisha, India, where it is used for construction, handicrafts, and feed, adding to the local population's economic well-being.

T2

R7: Safe living for us, apart from providing our needs, we can make tools that we don't need to buy anymore. In addition, it is used or made into a table to put different foods which are called (dulang in bahasa sug term) it is primarily served during weddings which is why bamboo should be taken care of because it can give convenience to the people. (Excerpt 65).

The interviews highlight that bamboo can be used to construct many different items that they don't need to buy. They also mentioned that it can be fashioned into tables where dishes are given during weddings. Bamboo is historically significant in Southeast Asian civilizations, particularly in ceremonies and daily life. Bamboo from five genera and

thirteen species is used for a variety of purposes in northeastern Thailand, including food, medicine, equipment, building materials, and attractive plants (Surapon et. al., 2023).

T3

R7: Additionally, it has something special because its water can serve as a medicine for many types of diseases. (Excerpt 66).

Participants underlined that water from the bamboo can serve as a remedy for ailments. Bamboo water, obtained from bamboo plants, has long been utilized in Asian medicine for its therapeutic effects. According to research, bamboo plants contain bioactive chemicals such as phenols, flavonoids, and phytosterols, all of which contribute to a variety of health advantages. Furthermore, studies have shown that an aqueous extract from the *Guadua paniculata* rhizome has anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive properties, indicating its potential for treating pain and inflammation. Overall, bamboo water and extracts show promise in preventing diseases such as diabetes, cancer, and cardiovascular issues, making them valuable in medicinal applications (Abir et al., 2015).

4.9 Have you witnessed any positive impacts of bamboo farming on sustainable agriculture practices or food security in your Barangay (Tangkuan Omar, Sulu)?

T1 Importance of bamboo

R1: The importance of bamboo is that if you want it to grow healthy, it should have a tree beside it so that the bamboo can lean underneath the tree. If it grows, the bamboo won't fall down in the air because it has a tree to lean on. (Excerpt 67).

R4: The importance of bamboo, is for the convenience of all if we don't weed it. For the relatives if they need bamboos, they can get them here. (Excerpt 68).

R10: It must be planted under a big tree if you want it to be big and tall. However, when it gets too big, the tree next to it will die. (Excerpt 69).

The interviews emphasize the necessity of planting bamboo. They said that if you want your bamboo to grow healthily and longer, you should place it beneath the tree. Bamboo can cause tree death owing to a variety of circumstances.

T2 Bamboo as a food

R2: The importance brought by bamboo cultivation is that when it's still growing, we will harvest it, and it can be eaten cooked as bamboo shoots (dabung in Bahasa Sug). (Excerpt 70).

R7: Secondly, bamboo shoots can be vegetables (Dabung in Bahasa sug term) and it is delicious to make vegetables, you can get more vitamins. (Excerpt 71).

R10: There are many things that can be done from bamboo, first of all bamboo shoots can be made into vegetables and it's delicious, it's even tastier than noodles. (Excerpt 72).

Participants appreciated bamboo shoots' originality, as well as their nutritious value in comparison to other cuisines. They claim that bamboo is tasty and nutritious.

4.10 At present, are bamboos being continuously planted or grown in your Barangay (Tangkuan Omar Sulu)?

T1

R1: For cultivating bamboo, like us we continue to cultivate bamboo and grow it. However, right now, it is not possible to grow it when it is planted if it does not have a fence because there are already many cattle here with us. That's the only thing that can't grow bamboo. (Excerpt 73).

R2: Yes, we continue to plant bamboo here. We are taking care of it now because it is a big help to us since we can use it to make floors for our house, or maybe use it to make bamboo chairs, and we can also eat it as a vegetable, which is the bamboo shoots. (Excerpt 74).

R3: There hasn't been much bamboo planted here since the animals in our province have eaten it. The bamboo should be gated but there isn't an iron fence, so even if it is, the animals would still nibble on some of it. (Excerpt 75).

R4: Regarding the planting of bamboo, nothing is being planted, but there is still bamboo growing here and being planted. (Excerpt 76).

R5: Yes, there is more, the cultivation of bamboo here is continuously growing, but are fences being built now, before the fence was made of bamboo, now the fence is protected by bamboo. Because if it is not fenced, animals such as cattle will eat it so it will not grow again. So here with us, we fence individually so that more bamboo can grow. (Excerpt 77).

R6: Anyway, there are still people who plant bamboo in our province because it is necessary to use fencing because the bamboo shoots are for cattle to eat. (Excerpt 78).

R7: As for me, yes the bamboo is still growing here because I clean it daily and I take care of it because this is what I use to meet my needs. (Excerpt 79).

R8: If like before, very few people take care of bamboo because the cattle eat it, but there are also those who are planted and it has a fence. (Excerpt 80).

R9: People here are still working, but if the bamboo doesn't fence here in our province, the cattle will eat the bamboo, but the plantations are still working. (Excerpt 81).

R10: It's just a little because the cows have eaten it. (Excerpt 82).

Participants emphasized the cultivation of bamboo in their area. According to them, the number of bamboo plants has decreased owing to cows eating them, but there are still a few planted. Bamboo can be a useful fencing material for protecting crops from harm caused by stray/wild animals such as cattle. According to research, bamboo bio-

fencing is a cost-effective and long-term animal deterrent that dramatically reduces crop losses (Sandeep et. al., 2022). Bamboo must be cultivated in local regions due to its numerous benefits. According to research, bamboo is good at restoring riverbanks, increasing soil fertility, and reducing soil erosion. Furthermore, bamboo is a sustainable alternative to lumber in construction, greatly enhancing structural performance while being renewable and locally available (S and Rittironk, 2022).

Conclusions

The main objective of this study is to investigate the ways in which bamboo can contribute to improving the quality of life and reducing poverty for small-scale farmers. It also examines the role of bamboo in preserving ecosystems, conserving soil, and providing benefits. Additionally, the findings highlighted the importance of bamboo for human well-being, livelihood, and the environment in barangay Tangkuan, Omar Sulu.

The results showed that the majority of the respondents were likely to agree with their own experience of how bamboo promotes a better health.

Furthermore, bamboo had a favorable impact on their livelihood because it was regarded as "strongly agree," implying that bamboo would most likely help them construct a sustainable lifestyle and serve as their potential income generator.

On the other hand, bamboo also greatly benefited them environmentally because it served as a natural water filter, improving water quality and producing a large amount of oxygen.

The interviews revealed that bamboo is used for a variety of purposes, including creating fences for crops such as sweet potatoes and bananas, which help the community's livelihood. Bamboo is recognized for its usefulness in supplying nutrition and revenue, particularly in locations where other food supplies may be scarce. Bamboo farming is seen as critical for livelihoods since it supplies materials for house constructions, fencing, home decorations and additional money through market sales. The uniqueness and importance of bamboo handicraft are recognized, emphasizing the specialized knowledge required for proper use and upkeep. The impact of bamboo growth on adjacent vegetation, such as trees, is discussed, emphasizing the importance of smart planting to avoid harmful outcomes.

Overall, people have asked that more bamboo be planted and cared for because it is a source of income, should be kept healthy, and improves the environment and general quality of life. After all, the more bamboo there is the more positive vibe it creates in society. Their well-being would increase with the amount of bamboo and a pleasant atmosphere in their surroundings, as this would have a positive impact on their livelihood and society. These three elements are related to one another because of this.

Recommendations

After conducting this study, the following recommendations are formulated.

To the LGU

The researchers recommends to have a training regarding bamboo in terms of livelihood, promoting bamboo-based livelihood opportunities within the community, the way on how bamboo served as a source of income and construction materials. Additionally the Barangay needs to motivate the inhabitants to organize and grow more bamboo in the Barangay.

To the residents of Barangay Tangkuan Omar Sulu

The researchers encourages the residents to plant more bamboo in their area as it is used in their daily living in order to provide more sources of bamboo to promote much good environment, livelihood and as well as a healthy well-being.

To the future researchers

Due to the lack of local study, the researchers encourage the future researchers to further more expand the study about the interconnectedness of well-being, livelihood and the environment, and explore more about the importance and uses of bamboo.

To encourage growth, the barangay needs to motivate the inhabitants to organize and grow bamboo in the barangay. The provision of training along with advice on proper planting, care, and maintenance enables successful growth. Promoting bamboo-based livelihood opportunities within the community is important. Encouraging community members to plant more bamboo and establish bamboo plantations in suitable areas within the barangay is essential. Providing training and support on proper planting techniques, maintenance, and care will ensure successful growth. Since bamboo has a lot of usage and being used by the residents in various ways, the following recommendations have been formulated. Firstly, the people in the society well instructed to plant more bamboo, as it is use in their daily living, and will be compelled to produce various ways on how bamboo become more sub profitable. Secondly, conducting practices on the livelihood in terms of bamboo-based initiatives, such as demo farming, on how to plant bamboo properly. Thirdly, understanding the significance between the well-being, livelihood and environment, while these three factors are interconnected, these factors' interplay, give insights to researchers about possible trade-offs or synergies as well as how to enhance well-being, promote sustainable livelihoods and mitigate negative environmental impacts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study on the multifaceted impact of Bamboo on Human well-being, livelihood, and the environment is guided by a strong commitment to ethical principles. The researchers were obtained, informed consent from all participants, ensuring a clear understanding on the study's purpose and procedures. Participants was assured that their

information is treated with the utmost confidentiality and handled securely. Participation in the study is entirely voluntary, and participants reserved the right to withdraw at any point without facing negative consequences.

The researchers pledged to uphold ethical principle throughout the research process. Confidentiality and privacy was rigorously maintained during data analysis, and results was presented in an unbiased manner.

Research finding was disseminated through appropriate channels with a paramount focus on protecting participant's privacy and confidentiality.

The researchers were dedicated to continuously assessing and addressing any ethical issues that aroused during the study. The protocol ensures that the research is conducted with the utmost respect for ethical standards and the individual who generously contributed to the study.

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